

Kinetic Studies of the Reaction Between Bromine and Mandelic Acid (Influence of Hydrogen Ion Concentration)

B. S. RATHOR & K. C. GROVER

Department of Chemistry, Jodhpur University, Jodhpur

Received 20 September 1969; revised MSS received 6 March 1972

The kinetics of the oxidation reaction of mandelic acid with bromine has been studied. The reaction has been found to be of first order with respect to each of the reactants, the total order being two. The values of ΔE , ΔF and ΔS were found to be 10.96 K.Cal./mole., 12.61 K.Cal./mole and -7.05 e.u. at $pH \sim 7.15$. The reaction rate has been found to be maximum at $pH \sim 8.19$ and decreases on both sides of this range. The reactive species has been found to be a combination of hypobromous acid and bromine molecule with $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$. The reaction mechanism can be represented via the attack of the oxidant on the carboxylate ion.

Bromine has already been used as an oxidant in acidic¹⁻⁵ and alkaline⁶ solutions. However, much work does not seem to have been done on the oxidation of mandelic acid with bromine. Here, the present authors have estimated mandelic acid with this reagent and studied its reaction mechanism. The oxidation proceeds to the stage of benzaldehyde which was confirmed by its smell and formation of dimedon derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were B.D.H. AnalaR products and were used without any further purification.

To 25 ml. of 0.025 molar bromine solution (containing 16 gms. KBr per litre) was added the requisite quantity of buffer solution. After 30 min. at constant temperature, 25 ml. of 0.025 molar mandelic acid solution (kept at the same temperature) were added (except in case of Tables 1A and 1B) and the whole made upto 100 ml. at this temperature. The timer was started during the mixing. Samples (10 ml.) were removed at known intervals and to it were added 8 ml. of 0.1 N KI solution and 7.0 ml. N H₂SO₄. The iodine evolved was titrated against 0.005 N sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. The difference between the two titre values (i.e., of blank and that of reaction mixture) at definite intervals of time represented the amount of mandelic acid oxidised at a particular stage. The hypo-bromite content of the solution was determined by arsenite method⁷ and used for the calculation of rate constants.

Reaction Rates : The following tables indicate the nature of the results obtained. Graphs were plotted for all results and the specific rate constants k_1 (first order) (Table 1A and 1B) and k_2 (second order) using equivalent concentrations of reactants (Tables 2 (A & B), 3) $\frac{\Delta}{\Delta t}$ obtained from the slopes of $\log(a-x)$ and $1/(a-x)$ respectively against time in minutes.

TABLE 1 (A)

(First order constant using excess of bromine)

Hypobromite = $12.40 \times 10^{-3} M$	Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$
Mandelic acid = $1.24 \times 10^{-3} M$	Sodium thiosulphate = $0.01 N$
Mean pH = 7.15	$k_1 = 1.81 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min.}^{-1}$

TABLE 1 (B)

(First order constants using excess of sodium mandelate)

Hypobromite = $1.165 \times 10^{-3} M$	Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$
	Sodium thiosulphate = $0.001 N$
Sodium mandelate $\times 10^{-2} M$	5.0 2.0 1.66 1.25
$k_1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min.}^{-1}$	0.613 0.255 0.211 0.156
$k_1/\text{sodium mandelate}$	0.123 0.127 0.127 0.125
Mean value of $k_1/\text{sodium mandelate} = 0.126 \pm 0.003 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ min.}^{-1}$	

TABLE 2 (A)

(Influence of temperature on reaction rate)

Hypobromite = $6.20 \times 10^{-3} M$	Mandelic acid = $6.20 \times 10^{-3} M$
pH of solution = 7.15	

Temperature °C	k lit. mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹ $\times 10^{-2}$
25	17.33
30	23.60
35	44.33

TABLE 2 (B)

(Effect of addition of salts on reaction rate)

Hypobromite = $5.975 - 6.20 \times 10^{-3} M$
Mandelic acid = $5.975 - 6.20 \times 10^{-3} M$

Nature of salt	Salt (molarity)	k lit. mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹ $\times 10^{-2}$
Nil	—	23.60
NaCl	0.025	26.93
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.025	30.53

TABLE 3

*(Reaction with unbuffered and buffered hypobromous acid)*Hypobromous acid = $5.925-6.125 \times 10^{-3}M$ Mandelic acid = $5.925-6.125 \times 10^{-3}M$ Temp. = $30^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$; Sodium thiosulphate = $0.005N$

	Mean <i>pH</i>	$\frac{k}{\text{lit. mole}^{-1} \text{sec.}^{-1}} \times 10^{-2}$
Unbuffered hypobromous acid	3.10	7.73
Buffered hypobromous acid	8.50	77.73

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It has been possible to oxidise mandelic acid quantitatively to benzaldehyde with bromine at $pH \sim 8$ within a time limit of 1 hour at 25° using 50% excess of the oxidant.

The reaction has been shown to be of first order with respect to each of the reactants (Tables 1A & 1B)—the total order being 2. The reaction has been shown to be fastest as $pH \sim 8.19$. The addition of electrolytes like SO_4^{2-} and Cl^{-} had a positive effect on reaction rate (Table 2(B)). Preliminary experiments in presence of sodium nitrate showed no effect on the rate of reaction. Hence, no precaution was taken to keep the ionic strength constant in this case.

The energy, of activation entropy and free energy were found to be 10.96 k.cal./mole., 7.05 e.u. and 12.61 k.cal./mole at $pH \sim 7.15$ (Table 2(A)).

Experimentally, it has been shown that no complex formation is involved in the system as shown by the fact that a plot of $1/k$ against $\frac{1}{\text{sod. mandelate}}$ gives a straight line which passes through the origin (Table 1B, Fig. 1). The absence of a free radical is indicated by the negative test with mercuric chloride. The fact that the reaction is fast in alkaline medium ($pH \sim 8.19$) agrees quantitatively with the assumption that the anion of the substrate is oxidised much more rapidly than the undissociated molecule.

Reactive species : There exists an equilibrium between the four oxidising components via. $[Br_2]$, $[HBrO]$, $[BrO^{-}]$ and $[Br_3^{-}]$. A little bromous acid $[HBrO_2]$ is also formed which being unstable changes into hypobromous acid. The disproportionation of hypobromite into bromate is not considered since bromate has no effect on mandelic acid in alkaline solution.

Taking into consideration the formation of the ions mentioned above, we have

Out of the above mentioned four oxidising species $[\text{BrO}^-]$ is maximum at high values of $p\text{H}$ (which is not the case, here) and, thus, one or more of the remaining species may be responsible for oxidation.

Studies on the effect of added bromide (0.2 M to 0.3 M) were conducted and the reciprocal of the observed rate constant (k_{obsd}) plotted against bromide concentration, C . A plot of $1/k_{obsd}$ vs C gave a straight line with a slope equal to $1/k_{Br_2} \cdot K_3$ (where K_3 is the dissociation constant of tribromide). This is shown in figure 2 where we used $k_{Br_2} = 6.25 \times 10^{-3}$ for k_{obsd} in the total absence of bromide and obtained a value of $K_3 = 0.046$, which is not very far from the value ($K_3 = 0.056$) given in the literature⁸. This shows that K_3 plays a negligible role in the oxidation reaction and we are left with HOBr or Br_2 as the reactive species.

Under these circumstances, the rate equation is :

$$k_{obsd} = (k_{Br_2}[\text{Br}_2] + k_{HOBr}[\text{HOBr}])(a-x)$$

(where a = initial concentration of oxidising agent and x = no. of moles litre⁻¹ reacted).

The equation can be written in the form :

$$C[1+(C/K_3)-k_{Br_2}/k_{obsd.}] = \frac{k_{HOBr}K_1/[H^+]}{k_{obsd}} - \frac{K_1}{[H^+]}$$

where K_1 is the hydrolysis constant of bromine.

In order to decide between these two species, HOBr and Br_2 , two possibilities⁹ may be considered.

1. The value of k_{Br_2} remains unaffected by pH and the increase in k_{obsd} with increasing pH (upto pH ~ 8) is due to the contribution of HOBr to the observed rate.

If this be so, the reciprocal of the observed rate constant k_{obsd} against $C[1+(C/K_3)-k_{Br_2}/k_{obsd.}]$ (Figure 3) should be a straight line passing through $(-K_1/[H^+])$, for $1/k_{obsd} = 0$. The theoretical value of $(-K_1/[H^+])$ is indicated by a cross on the x-axis. Though a straight line was obtained in this case, it did not pass through $(-K_1/[H^+])$, for $1/k_{obsd} = 0$. From the above plot by an extrapolation of the straight line to $1/k_{obsd} = 0$, we got a value

of $K_1 = 19.0 \times 10^{-9}$ which is nearer to (the accepted value of $K_1 = 11.3 \times 10^{-9}$). Thus, the assumption that $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$ is supported by these results.

2. On the basis of second possibility i.e., $k_{HOBr} \ll k_{Br_2}$ and neglecting hypobromous acid in the above equation, we can write

$$\frac{1}{k_{obsd}[1+(C/K_3)]} = \frac{K_1/[H^+]}{k_{Br_2}C[1+(C/K_3)]} + \frac{1}{k_{Br}}$$

If $k_{HOBr} \ll k_{Br_2}$, it can be noted that $k_{obsd}[1+(C/K_3)]$ would be the value of k_{Br} if the formation of HOBr were totally suppressed in presence of excess bromide.

The values of $[k_{obsd}\{1+(C/K_3)\}]^{-1}$ against $[C\{1+(C/K_3)\}]^{-1}$ were plotted where K_3 is the dissociation constant of tribromide. The intercept is the reciprocal of k_{Br_2} and the slope is equal to $\frac{K_1}{k_{Br_2}[H^+]}$ where K_1 is the hydrolysis constant of bromine. A straight line was obtained in this case (Figure 4). From its intercept k_{Br_2} was found to be 6.15×10^{-3} .

MANDELIC ACID VS BROMINE FIG 4

From the slope, the value of $K_1/(H^+)$ was calculated and found to be 35.42×10^{-2} or $K_1 = 134.61 \times 10^{-9}$ which differs from the theoretical value. Thus, we can conclude that $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$.

The first assumption is also supported by the results with bromine free hypobromous acid (Table 3) which was prepared by the method of Y. Knoller and B. Perlmutter-Hayman¹¹.

Besides, a plot of experimental values of rate constants *vs* calculated values of concentrations of the main reactive species $[HBrO] \times [C_6H_5CHOHCOO^-]$ at middle stage of the reaction showed the two curves to be almost identical (Figure 5). Thus, the reactive species in this case is a combination of $HBrO + Br_2$ with $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$.

Reaction Mechanism: At higher values of *pH* (the reaction being maximum at *pH* ~ 8.19), some of the experimental facts could not be explained by assuming the oxidation at the alcoholic group, which may occur at the carboxylate ion via C-C fission as indicated by the production of CO_2 (cf. oxidation of glycol or pinacol by periodate)¹².

Gyani and Prasad¹³ have isolated benzoyl formic acid in the oxidation of mandelic acid by chromic acid where the oxidation is assumed to be at the alcoholic group via C-H fission. The non-formation of benzoyl formic acid in the present case rules out this possibility. Thus, the oxidation of mandelic acid by hypobromous acid or molecular bromine can be represented by the attack of the oxidant at the carboxylate ion as shown below:

We are thankful to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head, Department of Chemistry, Jodhpur University, Jodhpur, for the grant of laboratory facilities and to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra, Head, Chemistry Department, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, for helpful discussions. One of the authors (B.S.R.) is thankful to C.S.I.R. for the grant of a fellowship.

REFERENCES

1. M. Roloff, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1894, **13**, 346.
2. A. Berthond and H. Bellenot, *J. Chem. Physik.*, 1924, **21**, 308.
3. E. Josefowicz, *Rocz. Chem.*, 1928, **8**, 123.
4. H. A. Liebhafsky and B. Makower, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, **29**, 597.
5. C. N. Hinshelwood, *J. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1947, 694.
6. K. C. Grover and R. C. Mehrotra, *Z. Physik. Chem. Neue Folge.*, 1958, **14**, 345.
7. P. Engell, A. Oplatka and B. Perlmutter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 2010.
8. G. Jones and S. Backstrom, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **89**, 3555.
9. B. Perlmutter Hayman and Y. Weismann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 668.
10. H. A. Liebhafsky, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 1500.
11. Y. Knoller and B. Perlmutter Hayman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 3213.
12. Charles, C. Prince and Harry Kroll, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2726; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1536.
13. B. P. Gyani and S. N. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 155.

